

ROLLING AND SLIDING WEAR PROPERTIES OF UNCURED/CURED HNBR AND PARTLY POLYMERIZED CBT HYBRID COMPOUNDS

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SUMMARY

The phase structure and rolling and sliding wear properties of hybrids composed of hydrogenated acrylonitrile/butadiene rubber (HNBR) and cyclic butylene terephthalate oligomers (CBT) (1:1 in weight) were studied by extraction, differential scanning calorimetry, dynamic-mechanical thermal analysis and various wear test rigs, respectively.

Key words: HNBR, cyclic butylene terephthalate (CBT), hybrid, rolling and sliding wear, wear mechanisms

INTRODUCTION

Rubber/thermoplastic combinations offer various benefits, such as lower costs, property improvements, easy recycling over traditional rubbers. Rubber/thermoplastic hybrids often possess attractive tribological performance making them suitable for engineering applications. Some research works already addressed the tribology of such blends and thermoplastic dynamic vulcanizates (e.g. [1-3]). A very promising new option is to combine rubbers with cyclic butylene terephthalate oligomers (CBT). Note that CBT can be polymerized above its melting ($T \approx 140-150$ °C) into polybutylene terephthalate (pCBT). The related temperature range is closely matched with that of rubber curing. Moreover, the polymerization temperature and time can be adjusted to the requirements of the rubber curing by selecting suitable catalysts [4, 5]. The designation pCBT considers that its properties (molecular mass, crystallinity, ductility) somewhat differ from those polybutylene terephthalates which have been produced in traditional polycondensation processes.

CBT can work as active filler in cured rubbers when partly or fully polymerized (designated further on by (p)CBT and pCBT, respectively). The stiffness and strength of the related hybrids are highly enhanced compared to the parent rubber [6, 7]. In addition,

the CBT acts as viscosity reducer for the parent rubber mixes. Preliminary results on the tribological proportion of such hybrids were very encouraging.

Accordingly, in this paper the rolling and sliding friction and wear of hydrogenated acrylonitrile/butadiene rubber (HNBR) based compounds containing partly polymerized CBT ((p)CBT) were studied against steel in various testing configurations. The HNBR itself was uncured or fully cured (unHNBR and curedHNBR, respectively). The rolling/sliding tests covered orbital rolling ball-on-plate (Orbital-RBOP), pin-on-plate (POP), roller-on-plate (ROP) and oscillating cylinder on plate (fretting) configurations under unlubricated condition. Extraction, differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and dynamic-mechanical thermal analysis (DMTA) were adopted to clarify the CBT conversion to pCBT, and to get a deeper understanding in the phase structure of the hybrid compounds. The coefficient of friction (COF) and the specific wear rate (W_s) were determined. The worn surfaces were investigated in scanning electron microscope (SEM) and white light profilometer and the related wear mechanisms were analyzed.

Experimental

Preparation of unHNBR- and curedHNBR-(p)CBT

Before mixing the cyclic butylene terephthalate (CBT® 160, Cyclics Europe, Schwarzheide, Germany) with the hydrogenated acrylonitrile/butadiene rubber (HNBR) (Therban® LT VP/KA 8882 of Lanxess, Leverkusen, Germany; acrylonitrile content: 21%, Mooney viscosity ML(1+4)100 °C = 74) both materials have been dried separately in an oven at 80 °C under vacuum overnight. The HNBR/CBT ratio in the corresponding recipe was 1:1. The compounding was done as described below. First, HNBR was put in a Brabender laboratory kneader (50 cm³, type: Brabender Plasticorder 814600, Brabender, Duisburg, Germany) and mixed at 190 °C for 3 min. The revolution of the kneader was 30 min⁻¹. Then the CBT was added and the mixing processing lasted 30 min at the same temperature. Note that the HNBR did not contain curatives, so HNBR was not cured in the corresponding mixes. The mixes, dried overnight under the same condition as the parent HNBR and CBT, were pressed in a hot press (Collin P 200 E; Dr. Collin GmbH, Ebersberg, Germany) at 230 °C for 5 min into ca. 2 mm thick sheets. The obtained hybrid is referred to as unHNBR-(p)CBT to manifest that the HNBR was uncured in the compound and the CBT partly polymerized.

The composition of curedHNBR-(p)CBT was: HNBR 100 part, CBT 100 part, di(tert-butylperoxyisopropyl)benzene (Perkadox 14S-F1, Akzo Nobel, Düren, Germany) 3 part, triallyl cyanurate (Perkalink 300-50d, Akzo Nobel) 3 part, ZnO 2 part and MgO 2 part. The curatives were introduced in the HNBR/CBT blend after 20 min of mixing at T= 190 °C. Dynamic vulcanization of the HNBR occurred during 10 min additional mixing. “Cured” in the designation means that HNBR was dynamically cured (i.e. during melt mixing) in presence of peroxide curatives. 2 mm thick sheets were gained by the same hot pressing technology adopted for the unHNBR-(p)CBT series.

Testing

Extraction

Because chloroform can solve only the unpolymerized CBT and does not attack the polymerized one, it was chosen as solvent for extraction. Note that uncured HNBR dissolves in chloroform, too. This has been considered when calculating the CBT conversion.

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

DSC traces were registered in a DSC device (DSC821e of Mettler Toledo, Giessen, Germany) in a temperature range from 25 to 250 °C at heating and cooling rates of 10 °C/min.

Dynamic-mechanical thermal analysis (DMTA)

DMTA spectra were measured on rectangular specimens in tensile mode at a static preload 0.01 N with a superimposed sinusoidal 0.01% strain. The frequency was 10 Hz and the spectra were registered in a broad temperature range (from -100 °C to +240 °C) with a Q800 device of TA Instruments (New Castle, DE, USA). From -100 °C, the temperature was increased by 5 °C and stabilized for 3 min for each step.

Density determination

For the density determination the Archimedes principle (buoyancy method with water) was adopted according to the ISO 1183 standard.

Rolling and sliding

Testing

The unlubricated rolling friction and wear of the composites were evaluated in an orbital rolling ball (steel)-on-plate (rubber) (Orbital-RBOP) test configuration. The rubber sheet was worn by a steel ball (100Cr6, diameter: 14 mm, arithmetical roughness R_a : 1 μm), which rolled along a circular path (diameter: 33 mm) when pushed by a defined normal load against the rubber sheet. The parameters set for this configuration were normal load: 90 N, revolution: 280 rpm, duration: 3 h.

Sliding friction and wear characteristics were assessed in pin (steel)-on-plate (rubber) (POP), roller (steel)-on-plate (rubber) (ROP) and oscillating cylinder (steel) on plate (rubber) (fretting) tribotests under dry condition.

POP is fixed in a Wazau device (Berlin, Germany), in which a steel pin (100Cr6, $R_a < 1 \mu\text{m}$) with a hemispherical head of 10 mm diameter rotated along a circular path of 33 mm diameter. The pin was pressed on the rubber plate with a given load. The following parameters were chosen for this configuration - normal load $\leq 3 \text{ N}$, sliding speed 250 mm/s, duration 90 min.

In ROP, a self-rotating steel roller (9SMnPb28k, diameter: 10 mm, width: 20 mm, $R_a \approx 0.9 \mu\text{m}$) was pressed against a rubber strip of $\leq 9 \text{ mm}$ width in a SOP 3000 tribotester (Dr Tillwich GmbH, Horb-Ahldorf, Germany). The test parameters were as follow: load $\leq 4 \text{ N}$, sliding speed 250 mm/s and duration 90 min .

In the third tribotester (fretting) a steel cylinder was pushed by a defined normal load and oscillated on the surface of the fixed rubber specimen. The diameter and the contact length of the cylinder ($R_a \approx 0.9 \mu\text{m}$) were 15 and $\leq 15 \text{ mm}$, respectively. The applied experimental parameters were: normal load $\leq 30 \text{ N}$, frequency of the oscillation $\leq 20 \text{ Hz}$, stroke $\leq 5 \text{ mm}$ and duration $\leq 180 \text{ min}$.

All above test rigs allowed monitoring the dynamic coefficient of friction (COF) as a function of time. The specific wear rate (W_s) was calculated according to:

$$W_s = \frac{\Delta V}{F \cdot L} \quad (1)$$

where $\Delta V [\text{mm}^3]$ is the volume loss, $F [\text{N}]$ is the normal load, $L [\text{m}]$ is the overall rolling/sliding distance. The loss volume (ΔV) was calculated by measuring the depth and width of the wear tracks by white light profilometer (see later) and supposing the shape of the wear track is a half-ellipse.

The schemes of the above testing methods are depicted in Figure 1.

Failure

The worn surfaces were scanned in a MicroProf white light profilometer (Fries Research & Technology, Bergisch Gladbach, Germany) and in SEM (JSM-6300 of Jeol, Tokyo, Japan). The specimens were sputtered with an Au/Pd alloy in a device of Balzers (Lichtenstein) prior to SEM investigation.

Figure 1 Schemes of the test configurations of Orbital-RBOP, POP, ROP and fretting. This figure also shows the preparation of the samples for SEM investigations after Orbital-RBOP test (top right).

Results and Discussion

CBT conversion and phase structure

Extraction

The results of the chloroform extraction of the hybrids are listed in Table 1. CBT in unHNBR-(p)CBT partly polymerized, which is in concert with the DSC observation (see later). For the curedHNBR-(p)CBT, the pCBT content was deduced by considering the DSC results of unHNBR-(p)CBT in Table 1 (*).

Table 1 Density and CBT contents of the hybrids, their chloroform extracts and pCBT contents.

Designation, (Composition)	Initial CBT content [%]	Melt enthalpy of pCBT in first / second heating [J/g]	Density [g/cm ³]	Chloroform extract [%]	Polymerized CBT, pCBT [%]
unHNBR- (p)CBT	50	-19.18/-20.38	1.097	73.6	52.8
curedHNBR- (p)CBT	47.6	-13.62/-14.30	1.118	63.2	37.9*

DSC

Figure 2 shows the DSC results for the heating (up 1 and up 2) and cooling (down) phases of the hybrids containing equal amount of HNBR and CBT. One may notice the melting peak of the unpolymerized CBT at $T \approx 130$ °C and much larger melting peak of pCBT at $T \approx 200$ °C for both hybrids in the phase “up 1”. The peaks at $T \approx 165$ - 185 °C in the cooling stage is assigned to the crystallization of pCBT. In the second heating (up 2), the more prominent melting peak of pCBT, compared to the traces in “up 1”, reflects that additional CBT has been polymerized during the DSC “treatment”. This is confirmed by the enthalpy values of the pCBT melting peak, as indicated in Table 1.

Figure 2 DSC traces recorded for hybrids during heating (up 1 and 2) and cooling (down).

DMTA

Figure 3 displays the changes of the storage modulus (E') and loss factor ($\tan \delta$) as a function of the temperature ($T = -100 \dots 225 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). The glass transition temperature of the HNBR (T_g) was at $T \approx -25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ based on the $\tan \delta$ maximum of the related relaxation for the HNBR/CBT hybrids. The sharp decrease of E' as a function of T at the HNBR T_g suggests that HNBR forms the matrix in all systems studied. The E' of unHNBR-(p)CBT is smaller than its vulcanized counterpart (viz. curedHNBR-(p)CBT), as expected.

The storage modulus of the unHNBR- and curedHNBR-(p)CBT decreases gradually with the temperature above the T_g of the HNBR. One can observe a crossover of E' of unHNBR- and curedHNBR-(p)CBT with the plateau modulus of the neat HNBR at $T \approx 145\text{--}160 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Recall that this is matched with the melting temperature of the unpolymerized CBT.

A plateau-like range appears in the E' vs. T traces between 140 and $180 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for both compounds. This reflects the presence of unpolymerized CBT in the compounds considering the fact that the melting range of CBT is between 140 and $150 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Afterwards E' increases with the temperature suggesting the polymerization of CBT to pCBT. The above scenarios are observable also in the $\tan \delta$ vs. T traces where a broad mechanical loss peak can be found at $T = 150\text{--}180 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. As mentioned above, the appearance of this peak is due to the melting and subsequent polymerization of the CBT. So, the DMTA results corroborate that a part of the CBT polymerized in the blends, as indicated by extraction and DSC analysis results.

Figure 3 Storage modulus E' and loss factor $\tan \delta$ as a function of the temperature for hybrids. Note: E' of the neat HNBR was for forming a comparison with that of the hybrids.

Rolling and sliding friction and wear

Table 2 shows the COF and W_s of unHNBR-(p)CBT and curedHNBR-(p)CBT hybrids measured in Orbital-RBOP tests. One can get the impression that unHNBR-(p)CBT has the higher W_s and COF value than its cured counterpart. This indicates that curing of the HNBR matrix may improve the resistance to rolling wear.

For sliding friction and wear, the W_s of unHNBR-(p)CBT is higher compared to that of curedHNBR-(p)CBT in POP and fretting but lower in ROP. However, the COF of the cured hybrid is higher in all three test rigs.

Table 2 W_s and COF for the hybrids in Orbital-RBOP, POP, ROP and fretting tests.

	W_s [mm ³ /N·m]		COF	
	unHNBR-(p)CBT	curedHNBR-(p)CBT	unHNBR-(p)CBT	curedHNBR-(p)CBT
Orbital-RBOP	(2.46±0.38)E-03	(6.25±3.63)E-04	0.051±0.001	0.048±0.004
POP	(7.83±4.83)E-02	(2.64±1.10)E-02	0.948±0.349	0.968±0.241
ROP	(1.09±0.35)E-03	(7.59±4.94)E-03	0.809±0.022	1.523±0.442
Fretting	(1.44±0.14)E-02	(9.68±0.33)E-03	1.178±0.301	1.577±0.190

Failure during rolling wear

Figure 4 shows SEM photos taken from the rolling wear track of unHNBR-(p)CBT. Due to the additional spin of the ball when rotating with concentric revolutions, as described in Ref. [8], the wear track can be divided into three regions- cf. Figure 1. Figures 4a and c show the outer and inner regions, which are with additional forward and backward spin of the ball, respectively (cf. Figure 1). Figure 4b is the middle region between the outer and inner regions (centre region- cf. Figure 1). In the outer region powder-like debris can be observed (cf. Figure 4a). Network-like surface cracks dominate the centre region (cf. Figure 4b). Large-dimension fatigue cracks with prominent crack opening are found in the inner region (cf. Figure 4c). The curedHNBR-(p)CBT showed similar wear failure as unHNBR-(p)CBT. Comparing the related SEM pictures in Figures 4 and 5 one can notice that dynamic curing of the HNBR suppressed both the fragmentation and fatigue-induced surface cracking.

Figure 4 SEM photos taken from the rolling wear track of unHNBR-(p)CBT after Orbital-RBOP test. (a) outer region, (b) centre region, (c) inner region. Note: rolling direction is downward.

Figure 5 SEM photos taken from the rolling wear track of curedHNBR-(p)CBT after Orbital-RBOP test. (a) outer region, (b) centre region, (c) inner region. Note: rolling direction is downward.

Figure 6 demonstrates the crystals observed in the worn surfaces of unHNBR- and curedHNBR-(p)CBT. They are CBT crystals [6, 7], confirming that a part of CBT remained

unpolymerized in these blends. It is worth noting that CBT crystals could be located in the worn surface after the sliding wear experiments, too.

Figure 6 High magnification SEM photos taken from the rolling wear tracks of (a) unHNBR- and (b) curedHNBR-(p)CBT after Orbital-RBOP tests.

Failure during sliding wear

The worn surfaces of ROP and fretting show pronounced similarities with those of the POP tests, thus they are not expounded separately in this article.

Figure 7 shows SEM photos taken from the POP wear tracks of unHNBR-(p)CBT and curedHNBR-(p)CBT. Smearing dominates the whole worn surface of unHNBR-(p)CBT (cf. Figure 7a). Deformed stripes and fibrils caused by considerable plastic deformation are discernible in the wear track of curedHNBR-(p)CBT after POP (cf. Figure 7b). This indicates an increase in the COF. Interestingly, this was not accompanied with enhanced specific wear rate when compared to the unHNBR-(p)CBT.

Figure 7 SEM photos taken from the sliding wear tracks of (a) unHNBR- and (b) curedHNBR-(p)CBT after POP tests. Note: sliding direction is downward.

Conclusions

Various tests were adopted to investigate the phase structure and rolling and sliding wear properties of hybrids composed of uncured HNBR- and dynamically cured HNBR and (p)CBT. Based on the results of extraction, DSC, DMTA and unlubricated rolling and sliding wear tests, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- CBT was partly polymerized in both unHNBR- and curedHNBR-(p)CBT, the matrix of which was the HNBR rubber. Dynamic curing of HNBR increased the storage modulus above the glass transition temperature of the HNBR.
- curedHNBR-(p)CBT performs better in the respect of the rolling friction and wear compared to unHNBR-(p)CBT.
- Dynamic curing of HNBR under POP and fretting resulted in lowered W_s . While the COF of curedHNBR-(p)CBT is higher in POP, ROP and fretting tests compared to that of unHNBR-(p)CBT.

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